

TOWARD THE DEVELOPMENT OF A STANDARD FOR CHARACTERIZING THE ENERGY ABSORPTION OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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Abstract

As part of the design for vehicle crashworthiness, energy-absorbing structural elements have been successfully used in ground and air vehicles alike, and composites have shown great advantages in energy absorbed per unit mass of material. Key factors preventing the widespread adoption of composites in primary crash-resistant structures are the absence of specialized test methods for the characterization of energy absorption and the lack of sufficiently predictive analytical tools. This paper will show the current efforts of the CMH-17 (formerly MIL-HDBK-17) Crashworthiness Working Group (WG) to promote the standardization of a coupon-level specimen with which to screen material systems and compare laminate designs, as well as to generate guidelines for the realization of numerical models in advanced finite element programs.

Introduction

Recent studies [1] identified the key factors preventing the introduction of composites in primary crash-resistant structures in aircraft and automotive as the absence of:

- available design guidelines,
- accurate and inexpensive simulation tools,
- specialized test methods for the characterization of energy-absorption,
- accessible and adequate composite material property database.

A coordinated cross-organizational effort can lead to substantial advances in all these fronts through systematic investigations of current practices. Such effort has been undertaken by the Crashworthiness Working Group of the CMH-17 (Composite Materials Handbook), which comprises representatives from the aerospace and automotive industries, academia, and government laboratories and operates in parallel with ASTM Committee D-30 on Composite Materials.

The Crashworthiness WG is currently developing a standardized test method for measuring the specific energy absorption (SEA) capability of composite materials, and developing guidelines for analytical methods to effectively simulate composite structures under crash loading.

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Development of test standards

The vast majority of the work in the area of crashworthiness energy absorption has focused on thin-wall tubular specimens [2,3]. Yet, almost every investigator around the world has used different specimen geometries, setups, and loading rates to assess the energy absorption (EA) of their designs. Comparisons across different materials and stacking sequences are still very limited and only in a few occasions they have been performed systematically. The lack of an agreed upon test method makes the comparison of test results and research findings across the literature virtually impossible.

Limited work has been done with test geometries other than tubes, and it evolved in two directions [3-5]. The first approach features simple specimens, such as flat plates with or without built-in crush initiators, and very complex and costly anti-buckling support fixtures. The second approach features self-supporting specimen geometries, which require dedicated molding tool for manufacturing, but don't require the use of specific test fixtures.

Experimental work conducted to date has shown that composite energy absorption measurements are inherently related to test set-up characteristics through complex relationships. This applies to all specimen shapes, whether tubes, flat plates, or corrugated webs. Tubes present complex interactions due to the hoop constraint that off-axis fibers provide; flat plates present unknown degrees of interaction and constraint between the coupon and the support fixtures; corrugated webs have shown a moderate influence of corrugation geometry on measured SEA. However, it seems that self-stabilizing, open-section specimens such as corrugated webs may present a more acceptable means by which to measure a material's SEA and with which to validate material models in numerical simulations. This is in large part attributable to the fact that like tubes they do not require support fixtures, and like flat plates they do not have fiber in the hoop direction.

Figure 1. Corrugated plate specimen ready for testing in the test fixture, and close-up after crushing.

Figure 2. Flat plate specimen in the specialized test fixture, and close-up after crushing.

Figure 3. Exemplar plots of load, SEA, and total energy absorbed traces vs. stroke.

Validation of modeling strategies

Composite structures used in energy absorption applications are capable of sustaining large deformation with substantial load carrying capability. To predict the energy absorption, the constitutive models should be able to describe the response of substantially damaged material. The work by the members of CMH-17 Crashworthiness WG indicated that the capability of describing such responses in different codes with current composite models varies, but no one model can capture the complicated fracture morphologies. The group is coordinating a numerical round robin to compare and benchmark composite constitutive models in different codes (LS-DYNA, ABAQUS Explicit, PAM-CRASH, RADIOSS).

Composite constitutive models implemented in commercial finite element (FE) programs are continuum mechanics models. Composites are modeled as orthotropic linear elastic materials within a failure surface. The exact shape of the failure surface depends on the failure criterion adopted in the model. The failure criteria for laminated composites are typically strength based. Beyond the failure surface, the appropriate elastic properties are degraded according to the assigned degradation laws. By means of stiffness degradation, the nonlinear and softening responses of a composite material after its initial failure are described mathematically.

Depending upon the specific degradation law used in a model, the continuum mechanics models can be further divided into two broad categories. They are either progressive failure models or continuum damage mechanics (CDM) models (see Table 1). Progressive failure models use a ply discount method to degrade material properties. At the failure surface, the values of the appropriate elastic properties of the ply at the material direction are degraded from its undamaged state to a fully damaged state, which is often considered a complete loss and assigned a value of zero. The so-called progressive failure is realized through ply-by-ply failure in the perspective of a laminate. Progressive failure models have shown success [6] in axial crush simulations of composites exhibits brittle fracture, which are often observed in composite reinforced with unidirectional prepreg and fine woven fabric. Composites reinforced with fabrics of large tow size such as braid, continuous strand glass mat (CSM), and pultruded fiber glass tend to form continuous fronds at the crushing front instead of being crushed into debris. Our efforts using progressive models so far have not led to stable simulations for composites exhibit this type of failure [7]. Composite models based on continuum damage mechanics appear to be a better choice to model composites that form continuous fronds [7,8].

Table 1. Summary of composite material models available in the commercial explicit FE code LS-DYNA.

MAT	Title	Brick	Shell	T-shell	Degradation Law
22	Composite Damage	y	y	y	Progressive failure
54/55	Enhanced Composite damage		y		Progressive failure
58	Laminated Composite Fabric		y		Damage Mechanics
59	Composite Failure	y	y		Progressive failure
161	Composite MSC	y			Damage Mechanics
162	Composite MSC	y			Damage Mechanics

LS-DYNA simulation of a sine-panel

LS-DYNA explicit finite element analysis code is used to simulate the crushing of sine-wave composite panel structure enabling efficient characterization of energy absorption of composite. Figure 4 shows the geometry definition of the sine-wave panel with 12-ply lay-up $[0/90]_{3s}$ for a thickness of 0.075 in. (1.9 mm). Specimen length is 3.0 in. (76 mm). The material properties used in the model have been previously characterized for the highly toughened material system used in the sine crushing

experiments [4]. The specimen is standing freely and in contact with the crush plates, both the movable and the fixed ones. The contact surfaces are dry, rigid, as-milled steel plates. A 45-degree chamfer is used as trigger mechanism to initiate stable crushing.

The model uses MAT54 shell elements, while the trigger is modeled as a row of element at $1/3^{\text{rd}}$ of the actual thickness. Imposed test velocity is 1.0 in/ sec (25 mm/sec), which is noticeably below the observed dynamic thresholds [4], and has shown to give identical SEA measurements as the 0.05 and 0.5 in/ min tests (1.3 and 13 mm/min respectively) [5]. The model is shown in Figure 5, left.

The force-deflection curve obtained from the modeled is compared to the experimental one in Figure 5, right. The simulated curve is shown both as raw (unfiltered), as well as filtered using a 100 Hz SAE filter. The key parameters to facilitate crushing are the use of the “crashfront” elements available with LS-Dyna’s composite crush model, with “SOFT” parameter between the web and the plate. Through this feature, when a row of elements is deleted during the crush the remaining nodes are “pre-loaded” so that the element deletion will not lead to large dynamic oscillations providing a stable crush behavior. In the present study the most effective value for the soft contact parameter is has been found to be 0.6.

Using MAT54 for strain-base material failure model allows elements to erode when strain components fail at all element integration points. This technique deletes rows of elements as they come in contact with the loading plate, hence element debris or fronds are not expected to appear in the simulated failure morphology. Other investigators have shown [8,9] the formation of frond using material model MAT58.

Figure 4. Semicircular sine-wave panel geometry

Figure 5. LS-DYNA Finite Element Model and comparison with experiment

Notes

Paolo Feraboli and Mostafa Rassaian are the Chairs of the Composite Materials Handbook CMH-17 Working Group on Crashworthiness.

References

1. "Crashworthiness and Energy Absorption", CMH-17, Rev. G, Vol. 3, Ch. 14, Proceedings of the Crashworthiness Working Group.
2. Carruthers, J.J., Kettle, A.P. and Robinson, A.M., "Energy Absorption Capability and Crashworthiness of Composite Material Structures: A Review", Applied Mechanics Reviews, 51, 1998, pp. 635-649.
3. Feraboli, P., "Current efforts in standardization of composite materials testing for crashworthiness and energy absorption", 47th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Dynamics and Materials Conference, No. 2006-2217, Newport, RI, May 2006.
4. Feraboli, P., Garattoni, F., "Development of a test method for composite materials energy absorption: corrugated specimens", 48th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Dynamics and Materials Conference, No. 2007-2011, Waikiki, HI, Apr. 2007.
5. Feraboli, P., Deleo, F., Garattoni, F., "Efforts in the standardization of composite materials energy absorption", American Society for Composites 22nd Technical Conference, Seattle, WA, Sept. 2007.
6. Kim H, Ben G, Aoki Y, Impact Response Behavior of Rectangular CFRP Tubes for Front Side Members of Automobiles, 12th US-Japan Conference on Composite Materials, Dearborn, MI, Sept. 2006.
7. Xiao X, Mcgregor C, Vaziri R, Poursartip A, Progress In Composite Tube Crush Simulation, Proceedings of American Helicopter Society 63rd Forum, May 2007.
8. Xiao X, Johnson N, Botkin M, Challenges In Composite Tube Crash Simulation, Proceedings of the American Society for Composites 18th Technical Conference, Gainesville, FL, Oct. 2003.